

Urea and ammonium sulfate topdressed in three equal splits did not differ significantly (see table). Band application slightly increased grain yield and N uptake over topdressing. Additional benefit with band placement was probably due to the low rate of nitrification.

Application of ATC, a water-soluble chemical recommended for nitrification inhibition, did not influence yield and N uptake of rice, even at higher rates. This may be due to ineffective coating and leaching of the chemical from the bands. Potassium nitrate was the most

Influence of N source and a nitrification inhibitor (ATC) on yield and N uptake of wetland rice. Ludhiana (Punjab), India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	Apparent N recovery (%)
	Grain	Straw		
Ammonium sulfate (topdressed)	7.6	8.8	124.5	11.8
Urea (topdressed)	7.2	8.8	113.2	61.5
Potassium nitrate (topdressed)	4.8	6.3	80.6	37.9
Urea (banded)	7.8	9.2	122.6	76.1
Urea + ATC (banded)	7.7	9.3	119.8	13.5
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.6	0.8	5.4	—
Control (no N)	2.5	3.5	38.9	—

inefficient N source. Recovery of N from potassium nitrate was about half that from ammonium sulfate and urea. □

Effect of plant density and fertilization on rice yield and fertilizer efficiency

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We studied fertilizer efficiency at different N P levels and different plant densities, with IR6 as the test variety.

Plant density and NP level significantly affected yield (see table). The highest yield was at 20- × 20-cm spacing (250,000 hills/ha) and the lowest at 40- × 25-cm spacing (100,000 hills/ha). The highest yield was with

Effect of plant density and fertilizer level on rice yield and fertilizer efficiency. Muridke, Pakistan.

Spacing (cm)	Plant density (hills/ha)	Yield (t/ha) at indicated NP (kg/ha) level				Mean for plant density ^a (t/ha)	N efficiency (kg rice/kg N) at indicated NP (kg/ha) level			Mean for plant density (kg rice/kg N)
		0-60	60-60	90-60	120-60		60-60	90-60	120-60	
40 × 25	100,000	3.2	5.7	5.9	6.3	5.2 c	42	30	26	33
25 × 25	160,000	3.2	6.0	6.1	6.7	5.5 b	44	32	28	35
20 × 25	200,000	3.5	6.2	6.4	6.9	5.7 ab	45	33	29	36
20 × 20	250,000	3.7	6.4	6.7	7.2	6.0 a	46	34	29	36
Mean for fertilizer ^a		3.4 c	6.1 b	6.3 b	6.8 a		44	32	28	

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other.

120-26 kg NP/ha. Fertilizer efficiency was lowest at the highest level of fertilization, increasing gradually with decreased fertilizer. Fertilizer efficiency was highest at higher plant densities. □

Effect of method of applying *Azospirillum brasilense* on rice yield

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Azospirillum brasilense Tarrand *et al.* fixes atmospheric N in soil. We studied methods of applying bacterium to increase yield. Peat-based *A. brasilense* inoculum (6 kg/ha) containing 10⁸ bacteria/g of peat soil was used for all treatments.

For seed treatment, 60 kg of seeds were soaked for 24 h in 60 liters water containing 6 kg peat-based inoculum. The seeds were allowed to sprout, then sown in the nursery. For seedling treatment, seedling roots were dipped in

Method of application of *Azospirillum* on rice yield. TNRRI, Aduthurai, India.

<i>Azospirillum</i> application method	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Seed	87	8	8.0	4.9
Seedling	86	7	1.2	4.8
Soil	86	7	1.5	4.6
Seed + seedling	88	7	8.8	5.6
Seed + soil	89	7	1.4	4.8
Seedling + soil	86	7	8.3	5.5
Seed + seedling + soil	89	8	9.3	6.5
Uninoculated (control)	84	6	6.3	4.4
CD	3	1	1.4	1.0

400 liters water containing 6 kg inoculum for 20 min and transplanted. Soil application of the bacterium was done by mixing 6 kg inoculum with 15 kg sand and broadcasting in the main field before transplanting. Inoculum also

was split into two doses and given as seed + seedling treatment or seed + soil treatment or seedling + soil treatment. In the last treatment, inoculum was split into three doses and given as seed + seedling + soil treatment.